

ASPECTS OF DIVISION OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN RELATIVE ADJECTS

Masharibova Lobar Rayimberganovna

2nd year master student of the State University of World Languages of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6573345>

Annontation: This article discusses aspects of the relativity of adjectives in English and Russian.

Key words: Quality, theory, relative quality, adjective, comparative degree, practical, category, sentence.

Quality is a part of the word, without which our language cannot exist. And that's just that you don't have to create images. Not without an adjective, but even a simple subject can be illustrated. If we do not know the exact characteristics of an object, we can therefore almost predict and imagine what actions we can take in relation to this object, what we can do.

Every language, including Uzbek and English, has means for expressing the categorical semantics of adjectives. The study of these tools is of theoretical and practical importance. Adjectives are one of the most important components of the morphology of the Uzbek language and are of great theoretical and practical importance. To distinguish a grammatical category as a group of words, three features are necessary: morphological, lexical and syntactic. Observations on adjectives in the Uzbek language showed that these adjectives are present in the composition of adjectives, and therefore adjectives can and should be separated into a separate group of words.

Adjectives are similar to adjectives in that they express a sign of a person or object, becoming a determiner in speech. While adjectives represent a stable, stable sign of a person or thing, adjectives represent a sign of change, action.

Time expressed by adjectives is relative. It does not directly indicate the action of the action at the moment of speech. To what time it belongs is determined by the time when it is understood by contraction of the sentence, or by the time when it expresses the general content of the sentence. The fact that the adjective is mainly related to the horse and identifies the horse means that the adjective is close to quality in function and meaning. Uzbek adjectives in their lexical meaning determine the movement of objects. Adjectives also represent images of characters.

Every language, including Uzbek and English, has means for expressing the categorical semantics of adjectives. The study of these tools is of theoretical and

practical importance. Adjectives are one of the most important components of the morphology of the Uzbek language and are of great theoretical and practical importance. To distinguish a grammatical category as a group of words, three features are necessary: morphological, lexical and syntactic. Observations on adjectives in the Uzbek language showed that these adjectives are present in the composition of adjectives, and therefore adjectives can and should be separated into a separate group of words. In order to understand the essence of the problem, we need to move away from the established scheme. According to the classification in school textbooks on grammar, adjectives are included in the verb system. This does not allow a concrete idea of both grammatical categories, the verb and the adjective. As a result, the essence of both grammatical categories, the features of each of them remain unclear. In other words, the concept of an adjective is combined with the concept of a verb. That's the nature of the verb

Original and relative adjectives

By meaning, adjectives are of two types: a) original adjectives; c) relative adjectives. Adjectives that directly express the subject attribute, can express the attribute in degrees and freely take the suffix -rak, are called initial adjectives: sweet melon - sweet melon - sweetest melon; big fish - big fish - very big fish.

Adjectives that express the subject sign in relation to a place or time by likening it to another object and not taking the suffix -rock are called relative adjectives: , qi), formed with the help of suffixes: fruit tree, medical certificate, modern dress, spherical body, Margilan merchant, summer work, winter clothes, street yard, home conversation.

Relative adjectives do not rank character. Only relative adjectives formed by the suffix -li have a hierarchical feature: strong - strong - very strong, smart - smarter - very smart.

In the original adjectives, the sign intensifies and decreases: green - green, yellow - yellow, red - red, black. Relative qualities do not have this feature.

The original adjectives have a modal meaning: young, smart, plump. Relative qualities do not have this feature. Modal meanings can be expressed only in relative adjectives formed by the suffix -li: smart, beautiful, etc.

True adjectives can be associated with verbs: Speak correctly, even if you are crooked, (Proverbs). Relative adjectives cannot be combined with verbs. Only relative adjectives formed with -iy can be combined with a very small number of verbs (for example, modern dress).

Quality levels

The phenomenon of distinguishing a feature in one object in relation to a similar feature in another object is called quality levels.

There are three different levels of quality: simple level, comparative level and incremental level.

Attributes of a simple degree represent a characteristic of only one object. They represent a sign without comparing it with another sign. In simple adjectives, there are no adjectives or adverbs. For example, a large yard, a smart girl, a green peacock, a red apple.

At the comparative level, the attribute of one object is compared with the similar attribute of another object.

The comparative degree is formed by the suffix -rak. This indicates whether the extra character is greater than or less than.

For example: Excess of character: Ali's book is more interesting than Vali's book. Gold is heavier than silver. Lack of character: This room is smaller than the previous one.

The accusative case is formed by auxiliary words and indicates that the sign goes beyond the norm. Auxiliary words meaning gradual include: most, very, very.

References

1. N. Rasulova "Lectures in the native language", Tashkent, "Nurafshon ziyo yagdusi", 2017
 2. M. Gapporov, R. Kasimova "Grammar of the English language", Tashkent, "Turonlkbol". 2010
 3. G. Sapaev "Modern Uzbek language" Tashkent, 2009
- 4uz.denemetr.com